

Proceedings of
the 36th International Business Information Management Association Conference
(IBIMA)

4-5 November 2020
Granada, Spain

ISBN: 978-0-9998551-5-7

Sustainable Economic Development and Advancing Education Excellence
in the era of Global Pandemic

Editor

Khalid S. Soliman

International Business Information Management Association (IBIMA)

Copyright 2020

Conference Chair

Khalid S. Soliman, International Business Information Management Association, USA

Special Session Chair

Svetlana Drobyazko, European Academy of Sciences, United Kingdom

Conference Advisory Committee

John F. Affisco, Hofstra University, USA
Abdul Rahman Ahmad, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Malaysia
Omar Al-Azzam, University of Minnesota Crookston, USA
Hesham H. Ali, University of Nebraska at Omaha, USA
Ahmed Azam, DeVry University, USA
Najiba Benabess, Millikin University, USA
Az-Eddine Bennani, Reims Management School, France
Emil Boasson, Central Michigan University, USA
Regina Connolly, Dublin City University, Ireland
Rene Leveaux, University of Technology, Sydney, Australia
Susana de Juana Espinosa, Universidad de Alicante, Spain
Xiuzhen Feng, Beijing University of Technology, China
Mohammad Ayub Khan, Tecnologico de Monterrey, Mexico
Sherif Kamel, The American University in Cairo, Egypt
Najib Saylani, Florida State College at Jacksonville, USA
Magdy Serour, InContext Solutions, Australia
Amine Nehari Talet, King Fahd University of Petroleum & Mineral, KSA
Abraham G. van der Vyver, Monash University, South Africa

Program Committee

(it is IBIMA Policy to include a program committee member's name only after reviewing at least one submitted paper)

Erne Suzila Kassim, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Malaysia
Dariusz Wielgórka, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Rifelly Dewi Astuti, Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia
Marcin Kuzel, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Poland
Livia Durac, "Petre Andrei" University of Iași, Romania
Aristides Dasso, Universidad Nacional de San Luis, Argentina
Miroslav Malaga, University of West Bohemia, Pilsen, Czech Republic
Mais Osama Jaradat, University of Jordan, Jordan
Olga Zavydivska, Lviv State University of Physical Culture named after Ivan Boberskyi, Ukraine
Doina I. Popescu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Norhayati Baharun, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Malaysia
Iulian Furdu, Vasile Alecsandri University of Bacău, Romania
Jyothsna Priyadarsini Kunapareddy, Krishna University, India
Jiří Kutlák, University of West Bohemia in Pilsen, Czech Republic
Larisa G. Nesterova, South Ural State University (National Research University), Chelyabinsk, Russia
Dmitry L. Napolskikh, Volga State University of Technology, Russia
Anca Tamaș, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania

Olga V. Ruzakova, Ural State University of Economics, Russia
Ali Saleh Alarussi, Xiamen University Malaysia, Malaysia
Ana Alexandra Gora, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Angela S.H. Lee, Sunway University, Malaysia
Iulian Gole, Bucharest University of Economic Studies (Academia de Studii Economice din București), Romania
Eriki Emoarehi, Covenant University, Ota Ogun State, Nigeria
Sónia Paula da Silva Nogueira, Polytechnic Institute of Bragança, Portugal
Jolanta Witek, AJP University in Gorzow Wlkp., Poland
Richard Fedorko, University of Presov, Faculty of Management, Slovakia
Margareta Nadanyiova, University of Zilina, Slovakia
Corina M. Radulescu, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, Romania
Mohd Syuhaidi Abu Bakar, Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM), Malaysia
Hanna Waligórska, WSB Wrocław, Poland
Elevita Yuliaty, Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia
Marie Černá, University of West Bohemia, Czech Republic
Małgorzata Cwiek, Cracow University of Economics, Poland
Natalia Petrishcheva, South-West state University, Russia
Paulina Golinska-Dawson, Poznan Univ. of Technology, Poland
Cristina Gabriela Cosmulese, Stefan cel Mare University of Suceava, Romania
Corina-Cristiana Nastacă, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Maria Claudia Diaconeasa, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Laura Mariana Cismas, West University of Timisoara, Romania
Anna Korombel, Czestochowa University of Technology (CUT), Poland
Marin Fotache, Al.I.Cuza University of Iasi, Romania
Krzysztof Dmytrów, University of Szczecin, Poland
Vincent Oh Kim Seng, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Julia Lysenko, South Ural State Humanitarian-Pedagogical University, Chelyabinsk, Russia
Tung-Liang Chen, Chung-Hua University, Taiwan, R.O.C.
Maria Kmety Bartekova, University of Economics in Bratislava, Slovakia
Violeta Sima, Petroleum-Gas University of Ploiesti, Romania
Mirko Palić, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Adela Sorinela Safta, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Doctoral for Economic School, Romania
Carmen-Elena Dobrotă, University of Bucharest, Romania
Nour El Houda Ben Amor, King Saud University, KSA
Hugo Augencio González Aguilar, Universidad Autónoma del Perú, Peru
Olena Sakovska, Uman National University of Horticulture, Ukraine
Camelia Delcea, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Boris Kovalenko, AN HEO «University associated with IA EAEC», The Herzen State Pedagogical University of Russia, Russia
Anna Wiśniewska-Safek, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Paulina Spânu, Politehnica University of Bucharest, Romania
Cristina Mariana Ene (Vasile), Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Grzegorz Warzocha, Wrocław University of Economics, Poland
Danuta Zawadzka, Koszalin University of Technology, Poland
Marta Wincewicz-Bosy, General Tadeusz Kościuszko Military University of Land Forces, Poland
Valery M. Abramov, Russian State Hydrometeorological University, Russia
Barbara Batóg, University of Szczecin, Poland
Anca Monica Ardeleanu, University of Bucharest, Romania
Dorota Balcerzyk, Military University of Land Forces in Wrocław, Poland
Jeong Chun Phuoc, Management & Sciences University, Malaysia
Adriana Dima, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Monica Boldea, West University of Timisoara, Romania
Andrey Dorofeev, Irkutsk National Research Technical University, Russia
Imran Riaz Malik, IQRA University, Islamabad Campus, Pakistan

Corina – Ionela Dumitrescu, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Wojciech Sadkowski, Jagiellonian University, Poland
Jana Majerova, University of Zilina, Slovakia
Victor Lorin Purcarea, "Carol Davila" University of Medicine and Pharmacy Bucharest, Romania
Kinga Krupcała, UTP University of Science and Technology, Poland
Damian Ostrowski, WSB University in Wrocław, Wrocław, Poland
Ismail El Moudden, Eastern Virginia Medical School, USA
Ahmad Suffian Mohd Zahari, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Malaysia
Milan Douša, Pavol Jozef Šafárik University in Košice, Faculty of Public Administration, Slovakia
Ioana Julieta Josan, University of Bucharest, Romania
Bahjat Fakieh, King Abdulaziz University, KSA
Arwa Mashat, King Abdulaziz University, KSA
Shamima Raihan Manzoor, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Cristian Ciurea, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Anna Sołtysik-Piorunkiewicz, University of Economics in Katowice, Poland
Aleksander Pabian, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Catalin Popescu, Petroleum-Gas University from Ploiesti, Romania
Natalia Manea, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Olena Prokopchuk, Uman National University of Horticulture, Ukraine
Anastasia Kurilova, Togliatti State University, Russia
Diaa Salama AbdElminaam, Benha & Misr International University, Egypt
Natalia V. Gryzunova, PRUE, Russia
Ivan Hul, Lviv State University of Physical Culture named after Ivan Boberskyj, Ukraine
Oksana Pirogova, Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Vladimír Bureš, University of Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic
Liudmyla Ilich, Borys Grinchenko Kyiv University, Ukraine
Velga Vevere, EKA University of Applied Sciences, Latvia
Alexandru Boicea, University Politehnica of Bucharest, Romania
Gabriel Koman, University of Zilina, Slovakia
Marek Zimnak, University of Lower Silesia, Poland
Sussy Bayona Oré, Universidad Nacional Mayor De San Marcos, Peru
Liudmila Oveshnikova, PLEKHANOV Russian University of Economics, Russia
Anastasiya A. Peshkova, Ural Federal University, Russia
Nicolae Goga, Politehnica University of Bucharest, Romania
Maria-Iuliana Dascalu, University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest, Romania
Michal Šimon, University of West Bohemia in Pilsen, Czech Republic
Maria P. Ivanova, National Research Tomsk Polytechnic University, Russia
Rolanda Kazlauskaitė Markeliene, General Jonas Žemaitis Military Academy of Lithuania, Lithuania
Andreea Elena Matic, "Dunărea de Jos" University of Galati, Romania
Igor Mayburov, Ural Federal University, Russia
Agnieszka Strzelecka, Koszalin University of Technology, Poland
Elisa Alén González, U. of Vigo, Spain
Bogdan-Cristian Chiripuci, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Yusliza Mohd Yusoff, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia
Joanna Krasodomska, Cracow University of Economics, Poland
Dalia Susniene, Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania
Falola Hezekiah Olubusayo, Covenant University, Nigeria
Mathew Shafaghi, University of Bolton, UK
Nadezhda A. Lvova, Saint Petersburg State University, Russia
Eluyela Damilola Felix, Landmark University, Nigeria
Noor'ain Mohamad Yunus, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Malaysia
Omar Bin Musa, Unitar International University, Malaysia
Norzalita Abd Aziz, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM) (National University of Malaysia), Malaysia
Delia Deliu, West University of Timișoara, Faculty of Economics & Business Administration, Romania
Tetyana Calinescu, National Aerospace University "Kharkiv Aviation Institute", Kharkiv, Ukraine

Ludvík Eger, University of West Bohemia, Czech Republic
Maria-Daniela Tudorache, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Branka Tuškan Sjauš, University of Zagreb - Faculty of Economics and Business, Croatia
Glorin Sebastian, Georgia Institute of Technology, USA
Elena Sibirskaya, Plekhanov Russian University of Economics, Russia
Nicolae Ionescu, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Aleksandra V. Loginova, Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Alexander Kuntsman, Saint Petersburg State University, Russia
James León Parra Monsalve, Corporación Universitaria Minuto de Dios – UNIMINUTO, Colombia
Tomasz Grodzicki, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Poland
Aurobindo Ogra, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Poland
Łukasz Wróblewski, WSB University, Poland
Pavel Juřica, Brno University of Technology, Czech Republic
Ricardo De La Hoz Lara, Universidad Libre, Colombia
Dawuda Alhassan, ASA College, USA
Ana Iolanda Voda, Social Sciences and Humanities Research Department, Institute for Interdisciplinary Research, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi, Romania
Raluca-Giorgiana Chivu, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Maha Alkhaffaf, World Islamic Sciences University, Jordan
Svitlana Bilan, Rzeszow University of Technology, Poland
Dmytro Solokha, Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, Ukraine
Liubov Shevchenko, Donetsk National University of Economics and Trade named after Mikhail Tugan-Baranovsky, Ukraine
Vyacheslav Makedon, Oles Honchar Dnipro National University, Ukraine
Svetlana Drobyazko, European Academy of Sciences, Coventry, UK
Maryna Chorna, Kharkiv State University of Food Technology and Trade, Ukraine
Lidiia Karpenko, Odessa Regional Institute for Public Administration of the National Academy for Public Administration under the President of Ukraine, Ukraine
Galina Pavlova, Dnipropetrovsk State University of Agriculture and Economic, Ukraine
Tetiana Hilorme, Oles Honchar Dnipro National University, Ukraine
Oleksandra Stoian, Petro Mohyla Black Sea National University, Ukraine
Martina Tomić Furjan, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Diana Naherniuk, Uman National University of Horticulture, Ukraine
Shehu Maikudi Musawa, The Federal Polytechnic Kaura Namoda, Nigeria
Alexandru Birsan, Bucharest University of Economics, Romania
Maciej Gliński, University of Agriculture in Krakow, Poland
Oksana U. Yuldasheva, S-Petersburg State University of Economics (UNECON), Russia
Victor Fedorovich Stucach, Omsk States Agricultural University, Russia
Ouail El Imrani, Abdelmalek Essaadi University, Morocco
Mihai Dinu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Lukasz Hadas, Poznan University of Technology, Poland
Osereme Omoike, Covenant University, Canaan Land, Ota, Nigeria
Klaudia Smolağ, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Michal Zoubek, University of West Bohemia, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Department of Industrial Engineering and Management, Czech Republic
Danuta Mierzwa, General Tadeusz Kościuszko Military University of Land Forces, Wroclaw, Faculty of Management, Poland
Nicolae Daniel Maita, Bucharest Academy of Economic Studies, Romania
Tadeusz A. Grzeszczyk, Warsaw University of Technology, Poland
Evgeniya K. Karpunina, Tambov State University, Russia
Blazenka Knezevic, Universtiy of Zagreb, Croatia
Morosan-Danila Lucia, "Stefan cel Mare" University of Suceava, Romania
Iryna Kyryliuk, Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University, Ukraine
Oksana Vinnytska, Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University, Ukraine
John Fredy Sánchez Mojica, Corporación Universitaria Minuto de Dios, Colombia

John Fredy Escobar Gómez, Corporación Univerisitaria Minuto de Dios, Colombia
Sergio Araya-Guzmán, Universidad del Bío-Bío, Chile
Andrei-Mirel Florea, "Dunarea de Jos" University of Galati, Romania
Chaikal Nuryakin, Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia
Radek Doskočil, Brno University of Technology, Faculty of Business and Management, Czech Republic
Stepan Chalupa, Institute of Hospitality Management in Prague, Czech Republic
Olena Bochko, Lviv Polytechnic National University, Ukraine
Ruslan Skrynkovskyy, Lviv University of Business and Law, Ukraine
Svitlana Plotnytska, O. M. Beketov National University of Urban Economy in Kharkiv, Ukraine
Băcanu Șerban Constanța, "Dunărea de Jos" University of Galați, Romania
Katarina Valaskova, University of Zilina, Slovakia
Marcin Sitek, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Sabrina O. Sihombing, Universitas Pelita Harapan, Indonesia
Boris Nikolaev, Penza State University, Penza, Russia
Yuliya Sunaeva, Russian University of Cooperation, Russia
Joanna Kurowska-Pysz, WSB University in Dąbrowa Górnicza, Poland
Dhafer Thabet, University of Ha'il, KSA
Justyna Łapińska, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Poland
Mauricio Antonio Bedoya Villa, Universidad de Medellin, Colombia
Ruxandra Curea-Pitorac, West University of Timisoara, Romania
Yuping Li, University of South Florida, USA
Dana Corina Deselnicu, Politehnica University of Bucharest, Romania
Marzena Graboń-Chałupczak, WSB University, Poland
Helena Štimac, Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek, Croatia
Anca Gabriela Molanescu, Bucharest Academy of Economic Studies, Romania
Olaleye Sunday Adewale, University of Oulu, Finland
Mirona Ana Maria Popescu, University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest, Romania
Joanna M. Moczydlowska, Bialystok University of Technology, Poland
Kehinde Adetiloye, Covenant University, Nigeria
Adedamola Olufunke Oluwunmi, Covenant University, Nigeria
Pedro Ferreira, University Portucalense, Portugal
Andrea Lučić, Faculty of Economics and Business Zagreb, Croatia
Abdallah Tubaishat, Zayed University, UAE
Andrzej Cwynar, University of Economics and Innovation in Lublin, Poland
Muhammad Imran Tanveer Opel, SZABIST University, Pakistan
Ulzhan Berikbolova, Korkyt Ata Kyzylorda University, Kazakhstan
Milena Janakova, Silesian university in Opava, School of Business Administration in Karvina, Czech Republic
Tomislava Pavic Kramaric, University of Split, Croatia
Corneliu Russu, Center of Industry and Services Economy, Romanian Academy, Romania
Yuliya Semenova, Russian State Hydrometeorological University, Russia
José Luis Silva Munar, Universidad de Atacama, Chile
Steliana Rodino, INCDSB-National Institute of Research and Development for Biological Sciences, ICEADR- Institute of Research for Agriculture Economy and Rural Development, Romania
Magdalena Zubiel-Kasprowicz, WSB University, Poland
Judyta Kabus, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Ljiljana Jovčić, Belgrade Academy of Professional Studies, Department Medical College of Professional Health, Serbia
Silviu Stanciu, "Dunărea de Jos" University of Galati, Romania
Amiruddin Ahamat, Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM), Malaysia
Octavian Dospinescu, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University, Romania
Andreea Anton, Ștefan cel Mare University of Suceava, Romania
Wojciech Szczepan Staszewski, University of Stettin, Poland
Marcel Kordoš, Alexander Dubček University in Trenčín, Slovakia
Paula Bajdor, CUT, Poland

Markus Günther, Bielefeld University, Germany
Ewa Stańczyk-Hugiet, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Martina Marchevská, University of Presov, Slovakia
Jolanta Kruk, WSB University in Gdańsk, Poland
Olga Rudakova, Central Russian Institute of Management – Branch of The Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy and Public Administration, Russia
Modupe Ake, Landmark University Omuaran Kwara State, Nigeria
Fran Galetic, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Łukasz Kuta, Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences, Poland
Alberto González Martínez, Universidad de León, Spain
Liudmyla Kliuchko, V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, Ukraine
Liudmyla Niemets, V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, Ukraine
Katarzyna Gadomska-Lila, University of Szczecin, Poland
Sebastian Kelle, University of Illinois, USA
Laurentiu-Stelian Mihai, University of Craiova, Romania
Mădălin-Dorin Pop, Politehnica University of Timișoara, Romania
Dorota Klimecka-Tatar, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Mejda Dakhlaoui, Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University – Dammam, KSA
Ibtissam Abarar, Université Hassan II, Morocco
Ramona Orăștean, Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Romania
Agnieszka Piasecka-Robak, University of Lower Silesia, Wrocław, Poland
Sharmila Rani Moganadas, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Stanciu Vasile Miltiade, Spiru Haret University, Romania
Jolanta Maria Ciak, WSB University in Torun, Poland
Justyna Hachoł, Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences, Poland
Joanna Zimmer, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Poland
Izabela Turek, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Angela Roman, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi, Romania
Olawale Yinusa Olonade, Covenant University, Nigeria
Grace Evbuomwan, Augustine University, Nigeria
Gabriela Marchis, Danubius University of Galati, Romania
Michal Paták, University of Pardubice, Czech Republic
Noor Azlinna Azizan, Prince Sultan University, KSA
Silviu Beciu, University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest, Romania
Marta Młokosiewicz, University of Szczecin, Poland
Faisal Zulhumadi, Universiti Utara Malaysia, Malaysia
Constanța Zoie Rădulescu, National Institute for Research and Development in Informatics, Romania
Kazimierz Nagody-Mrozowicz, The General Tadeusz Kościuszko Military University of Land Forces, Poland
Adekunle Emmanuel Adegboyegun, Adekunle Ajasin University, Nigeria
Christophe Kolski, Univ. Polytechnique Hauts-de-France, France
Manta P. Otilia, Romanian Academy, Romania
T. G. Vasista, Vasista Consulting and Performing Services OPC Pvt. Ltd., India
Ionuț-Claudiu Popa, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Marinela Mircea, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Marek Siemiński, University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn, Poland
Ilze Kacane, Daugavpils University, Latvia
Hafedh Ferchichi, Higher Institute of Technological Studies of Jendouba, Tunisia
Aslina Baharum, Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Malaysia
Małgorzata Kuraś, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Oana Mitruț, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Menaouer Brahami, National Polytechnic School of Oran - Maurice Audin, Algeria
Abd Rahman Ahmad, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Malaysia
Livia Sangeorzan, Transilvania University of Brașov, Romania
Olufemi Patrick Adeyeye, Federal University Oye Ekiti (FUOYE), Nigeria

Anna Zarkada, Athens University of Economic and Business, Greece
Diana Panait-Ioncica, ASE, Romania
Gabriela Tigu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Constanta-Nicoleta Bodea, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Kalubi Rawlings Jerry Mazuba, Peter the Great, St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Jelena Lukić, Modern Business School, Belgrade, Serbia
Mariem Gzara, University of Monastir, Tunisia
Olha Suptelo, V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National, Ukraine
Adriana Krawczyk, Amsterdam School of International Business, AUAS, Netherlands
Isibor Areghan, Covenant University, Nigeria
Anna Łupicka, Poznań University of Economics and Business, Poland
Irina Georgescu, Bucharest University of Economics, Romania
Iuliana Marin, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Claudia Carstea, "Henri Coanda" Air Force Academy, Romania
Anna Hamranová, University of Economics in Bratislava, Slovakia
Małgorzata Smolarek, Humanitas University, Poland
Adrian Nicolae Branga, Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Romania
Nikolay V. Gontar, Southern Federal University, Russia
Georgiana Armenita Arghiroiu, University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest, Romania
Irina Zaychenko, Peter the Great Saint-Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Muhammad Najib Razali, UTM, Malaysia
Waldemar Woźniak, University of Zielona Góra, Poland
Mohammad Aizat bin Basir, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu (UMT), Malaysia
Boris Kollár, University of Žilina, FPEDAS, Department of Economics, Slovakia
Alicja Szyszko, Jagiellonian University in Kraków, Poland
Maria Magdalena Roșu, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Svetlana Borisovna Vereshchak, I. N. Ulyanov Chuvash State University, Russia
Odunayo Paul Salau, Covenant University, Nigeria
Ioana-Alexandra Toader, University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest, Romania
Valentina Șuparschii, "Dunărea de Jos" University of Galați, Romania
Peter Busch, Macquarie University, Australia
Jayamalathi Jayabalan, University Tunku Abdul Rahman, Malaysia
Katarzyna Chruzik, WSB University, Poland
Adriana Reveiu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Katalin Gál, Partium Christian University, Romania
Mahmud Bashiru, University Science Malaysia, Nigeria
Radu D. Stanciu, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Irina Severin, Politehnica University of Bucharest, Romania
Adrian Kapczyński, Silesian University of Technology, Poland
Dumiter Florin Cornel, Vasile Goldiș" Western University of Arad, Romania
Ching Sock Lee, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia
Aneta Włodarczyk, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Ana Azevedo, CEOS.PP / ISCAP / P.PORTO, Portugal
Joanna Szymańska, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Mohammed Amine Hafiane, Université Mohammed Premier d'Oujda, Morocco
Mariola Piłatowska, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Poland
Irina Avdeeva, Central Russian Institute of Management, Branch of RANEPA, Russia
Elena Lacatus, Polytechnic University of Bucharest, Romania
Eko Sakapurnama, Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia
Ugochukwu Moses Urim, Covenant University, Nigeria
Tadeusz Dudycz, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Poland
Petr Doucek, Prague University of Economics and Business, Czech Republic
Olufemi Daniel Durodola, Covenant University, Nigeria

Nuno Adriano Baptista Ribeiro, Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Portugal
Alen Stojanovic, Faculty of Economics & Business Zagreb, Croatia
Azran Ahmad, MAMPU, Malaysia
Cristian Bucur, Petroleum-Gas University of Ploiești, Romania
Shaizatulaqma Kamalul Ariffin, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia
Michał Goliński, Warsaw School of Economics, Poland
Fadeke Esther Owolabi, Covenant University, Nigeria
Khalil Abakar Moussa Kaya, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Malaysia
Jelena Franjković, J.J. Strossmayer University of Osijek, Croatia
Katarzyna Grondys, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Oleh Lazarev, Uman National University of Horticulture, Ukraine
Gheorghita Vlad, Politehnica University of Bucharest, Romania
Nasina Mat Desa, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia
Hishamuddin Ismail, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Marius Bulearca, Center for Industry and Services Economics, Romanian Academy, Bucharest, Romania
Dmitry Rodionov, Peter the Great St Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Akunna Ebere Azuh, Covenant University, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria
Piotr Kuraś, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Agnieszka Stachowiak, Poznan University of Technology, Poland
Manaf Al-Okaily, Jadara University, Jordan
Rachmadi Agus Triono, Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia
Ionel-Bujorel Păvăloiu, University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest, Romania
Daniel Lang, Institut Mines-Télécom Business School, France
Ildikó-Csilla Takács, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Ionela-Roxana Glăvan, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Natalia A. Navrotskaia, Saint-Petersburg State University, Russia
Grzegorz Maśloch, SGH Warsaw School of Economics, Poland
Allal Mokeddem, University of Algiers 3, Faculty of economics, Commerce and Management Science, Management Department, Algeria
Arkadiusz Banasik, Silesian University of Technology, Poland
Marinela Vrîncianu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Poorna Prabhat Sunkara, JNTU Ananthapur, India
Igor Jovino Aguilar Alonso, Universidad Nacional Tecnológica de Lima Sur, Peru
Teresa Dieguez, IPCA, Portugal
Siti Munerah Abd Karim, Sunway University, Malaysia
Iván Quintanilla Areyuna, University of Atacama, Chile
Mohd Shamsuri Md Saad, Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka, Malaysia
Vladimir Plotnikov, St. Petersburg State University of Economics, Russia
Ryszard Szykowski, WSB Academy, Poland
Rossazana Ab Rahim, Universiti Malaysia Sarawak, Malaysia
Anca Gabriela Ilie, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Faculty of International Business and Economics, Romania
Bogdan Tiganoaia, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Daniel Homocianu, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi, Romania
Alin Emanuel Artene, Politehnica University of Timisoara, Romania
Iulia-Cristina Stanica, "Politehnica" University of Bucharest, Romania
Katarzyna Cheba, West Pomeranian University of Technology, Szczecin, Poland
Houssemeddine Derbel, University of Manouba, Tunisia
Jacek Batóg, University of Szczecin, Poland
Svetlana Globa, Siberian Federal University, Russia
Aleksandra Krajnović, University of Zadar, Croatia
Jan Chromy, Institute of Hospitality Management in Prague, Czech Republic
Tamara Iskra Alcántara Concepción, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, México
Agata Mesjasz-Lech, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Ștefan Cătălin Popa, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania

Olga Makarova, Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Olesya Valerievna Ivanchenko, Rostov State University of Economics, Russia
Gita Radhakrishna, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Elżbieta Rogalska, University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn, Poland
Ciprian-Octavian Truică, University Politehnica of Bucharest, Romania
Aw Yoke Cheng, Berjaya University College, Malaysia
Jayanty Kuppusamy, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Khairunesa Isa, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Malaysia
Ramona Dobre, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Ecaterina Daniela Zeca, „Dunarea de Jos” University of Galati, Romania
Honorata Howaniec, University of Bielsko-Biala, Poland
Constantin Ilie, OVIDIUS University from Constanta, Romania
Sławomir Jankiewicz, WSB University in Poznan, Poland
Maja Jokiel, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Haslinda Binti Husaini, Universiti Teknologi Mara (UiTM), Malaysia
Derweanna Bah Simpong, Universiti Malaysia Kelantan, Malaysia
Zikri Muhammad, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia
Olufunmilayo Tope Afolayan, Covenant University, Ota, Ogun; The Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State, Nigeria
Paul Ciprian Patric, Valahia University of Targoviste, Romania
Erin Olayinka, Covenant University, Nigeria
Maria Bernat, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Florin Stoica, Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Romania
Natalia Buchalska-Sugajska, UTP University of Science and Technology, Poland
Chuks Odiegwu-Enwerem, National Open University of Nigeria, Jabi Abuja, Nigeria
Anna Ivanova, Voronezh State University of Forestry and Technologies named after G.F. Morozov, Russia
Tomáš Sadílek, Prague University of Economics & Business, Czechia
Irina Voronova, Riga Technical University, Latvia
Stanislaw Urbanski, University of Science and Technology, Poland
Sorin Burlacu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Elena-Anca Paraschiv, National Institute for Research and Development in Informatics, Romania
Olufemi Adebayo Oladipo, Landmark University, Nigeria
Mariusz Urbański, Czestochowa UT, Poland
Hana Štverková, VŠB-Technical University of Ostrava, Czech Republic
Edyta Kulej-Dudek, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Ionuț Jianu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Nik Hazimah Nik Mat, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia
Daisy Kee Mui Hung, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia
Eva Lukášková, College of Business and Hotel Management, Czech Republic
Tatiana Borisovna Turishcheva, Plekhanov Russian University of Economics, Russia
Nicoleta Daniela Ignat, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Gabriela Prostean, Politehnica University of Timisoara, Romania
Ivonne Maria Gil Osorio, Universidad Libre Seccional Barranquilla, Colombia
Olga M. Kochkina, MGIMO, Russia
Adrian Moise, Petroleum-Gas University of Ploiesti, Romania
Ludmila M. Osinevich, Kursk State University, Russia
Barbara Wasilewska, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Joanna Muszyńska, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Poland
Petrică Sorin Angheluță, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Claudiu Cicea, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Erik Ružić, Juraj Dobrila University of Pula, Croatia
Małgorzata Rataj, University of Information Technology and Management in Rzeszow, Poland
Blanka Bazsova, VSB-Technical University of Ostrava, Czech Republic
Inese Lūsēna-Ezera, Liepaja University, Latvia

Tomas Broum, University of West Bohemia, Czech Republic
Dajana Barbić, Faculty of Economics & Business Zagreb, Croatia
Martina Hedvicakova, University of Hradec Králové, Czech Republic
Luis Nobre Pereira, University of Algarve, Portugal
Siti Noorsuriani Maon, Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM), Malaysia
Robert Ulewicz, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Karima Haoudi, Université Ibn Tofail, Morocco
Aleks Krasnov, Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Ratna Anggraini, Jakarta State University, Indonesia
Marcin Butlewski, Poznan University of Technology, Poland
Fabrizio Amarilli, Politecnico di Milano, Italy
Alina Romanovska, Daugavpils University, Latvia
Petr Rehacek, VSB-Technical University of Ostrava, Czech Republic
Elena-Simona Apostol, University Politehnica of Bucharest, Romania
Tatiana Olegovna Dyukina, Saint-Petersburg State University, Russia
Ovidiu Blajina, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Hanane Haddad, Abdelmalik Essaâdi University, Morocco
Izabela Czabak-Górska, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Vlatka Skokic, University of Split, Croatia
Adriana Alexandru, National Institute for Resear, ICI Bucharestch and Development in Informatics, Romania
Cristiana Doina Tudor, University of Economic Studies in Bucharest, Romania
Natalia Lytneva, Oryol State University of Economics and Trade, Russia
Violetta Kuzmina, SWSU South West State University, Russia
Anna Rybak, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Katarzyna Marek-Kolodziej, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Andreea Zamfir, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Katarina Haviernikova, Alexander Dubcek University of Trencin, Slovakia
Nor Fauziana Bt Ibrahim, Multimedia University (MMU), Malaysia
Sanja Broz Tominac, University of Zgareb, Faculty of Economics and Business, Croatia
Sanja Franc, Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Lawrence Uchenna Okoye, Covenant University, Ota, Nigeria
Prokopjeva Evgenia Leonidovna, Khakass Technical Institute – Branch of the Siberian Federal University, Russia
Agnieszka Knap-Stefaniuk, Jesuit University Ignatianum in Krakow, Poland
Dariusz Masłowski, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Nica Ionuț, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Elżbieta Sobczak, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Kamila Tomczak-Horyń, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Tuan Tran Hoang, University of Labour and Social Affairs (HCMC Campus), Viet Nam
Kalaiselvey Rethinam, AIMST University, Malaysia
Dorota Kwiatkowska-Ciotucha, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Rohoza Mykola, University Poltava University of Economics and Trade, Ukraine
Vera Samarina, Staryy Oskol Technological Institute, Branch of National Research Technological University "MISIS", Russia
Jolly Sahni, Prince Sultan University, KSA
Constantin-Marius Apostoae, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași, Romania
Wojciech Bożek, University of Stettin, Poland
Mariusz Tomczyk, War Studies University, Poland
Patricio Ramirez-Correa, Uniersidad Catolica del Norte, Chile
Okorie Uchechukwu Emena, Covenant University, Nigeria
Manuela Ingaldi, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Svetlana Morkovina, Voronezh State University of Forestry and Technologies named after G.F. Morozov, Russia
Paweł Buchwald, University WSB in Dąbrowa Górnicza, Poland

Dana Kiselakova, University of Presov in Presov, Faculty of Management, Slovakia
Elena Gasparovich, UrFU, Russia
Justyna Maria Myszak, University of Szczecin, Poland
Krzysztof Błoński, University of Szczecin, Poland
Petronela Cristina Simion, University "Politehnica" of Bucharest, Romania
Girjanauth Boodraj, University of Technology, Jamaica
Jakub Fučík, University of Defence, Czech Republic
Oleksandr Yukhymovych Yermakov, National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine, Ukraine
Alexei Dolzhenko, Rostov State University of Economics, Russia
Sylwia Konecka, Poznań University of Economics and Business, Poland
Lanre Amodu, Covenant University, Nigeria
Liliana Nicoleta Simionescu, The Bucharest University of Economics Studies, Romania
Oksana V. Haidai, Uman National University of Horticulture, Ukraine
Angie O. Igbinoba, Covenant University, Nigeria
Georgiana-Raluca Lădaru, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Ruxandra Dinulescu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Piotr Kułyk, University of Zielona Góra, Poland
Eugenia Czernyszewicz, University of Life Sciences in Lublin, Poland
Raisa Kozhukhivska, Uman National University of Horticulture, Ukraine
E. A. Borkova, Saint Petersburg State University of Economics, Russia
Katarzyna Kuziak, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Ovidiu-Iulian Bunea, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Karolina Rybicka, University of Technology, Poland
Ritesh Chugh, CQUniversity, Australia
Marius Schönberger, RISEBA University of Applied Sciences, Latvia
Hezlina Mohd Hashim, Universiti Teknologi PETRONAS, Malaysia
Pedro Neves Rito, Polytechnic Institute of Viseu, Portugal
Natalia Vladimirovna Lazareva, Saint Petersburg State University of Economics, Russia
Krzysztof Krukowski, University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn, Poland
Maja Pervan, Faculty of Economics, Business and Tourism, Croatia
Josef Botlík, Silesian University in Opava, Czechia
Beata Sofrankova, University of Presov, Faculty of Management, Slovakia
Liva Grinevica, Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies, Latvia
Mihai Caramihai, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Ivan Strugar, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Stefania Cristina Mirica, "Dunărea de Jos" University of Galați, Romania
Paweł Hanczar, Wrocław University of Economics, Poland
Yong Jing Yi, INTI International College Penang, Malaysia
Edyta Zajbert, University of Economics and Business, Poland
Alena Fedorova, Ural Federal University named after the first President of Russia B.N.Yeltsin, Russia
Hind El Ouazzani, Sultan My Slimane University, Morocco
Shirley Consuelo Honajzrová Banús, Institute of Hospitality Management in Prague, Czech Republic
Alicja Malgorzata Graczyk, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Felix Sadyrbaev, Daugavpils University, Latvia
Larisa Desfontaines, St. Petersburg Peter the Great Polytechnic University, Russia
António Eduardo Martins, Universidade Aberta, Portugal
Janusz Marek Lichtarski, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Elżbieta D. Nawrocka, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Olfa Mrabet, Université Centrale - Honoris United University, Tunisia
Vladimír Bolek, University of Economics in Bratislava, Slovakia
Magdalena Swacha-Lech, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Emese Tokarčíková, University of Zilina, Slovakia
Ivica Linderová, College of Polytechnics Jihlava, Czech Republic
Eva Malichova, University of Zilina, Slovakia

Noreha Hashim, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia
Robert Poskart, Opole University, Poland
Tatiana Shpilina, Russian State Social University, Russia
Małgorzata Rutkowska, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Poland
Ester Piwoni-Krzeszowska, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Elizaveta Gromova, Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Alicja Brodzka, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Ayodeji Olonode, Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye, Ogun State, Nigeria
Adrianna Guzowska, UTP University of Science and Technology in Bydgoszcz, Poland
Ekaterina Uskova, UrFU, Russia
Khatijah Omar, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia
Ricardo Correia, Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Portugal
Witold Kowal, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Marta Daroń, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Cezar Toader, Technical Univ. of Cluj-Napoca, Romania
Katarzyna Skrzypek, University of Zielona Góra, Poland
Alfred Paszek, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Lamyaa El Bassiti, Mohammed V University in Rabat, Morocco
Razana Juhaida Johari, Universiti Teknologi MARA Shah Alam, Malaysia
Justyna Śpiewak, UTP University of Science and Technology in Bydgoszcz, Poland
Agnieszka Stanimir, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Cristina Mohora, Politehnica University of Bucharest, Romania
Liviu-Adrian Cotfas, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Ivani Ferreira, Instituto Federal do Paraná – IFPR, Brasil
Ivana Nekvapilova, University of Defense, Czech Republic
Funke Omole, Covenant University, Nigeria
Oleksandr Shpykuliak, National Scientific Center «Institute of Agrarian Economics», Ukraine
Miroslaw Matusek, Silesian University of Technology, Poland
Iveta Linina, Turība University, Latvia
Gabriela Bucur, Petroleum Gas University of Ploiesti, Romania
Corina Marinescu, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Magdalena Kałol, Maria Curie-Skłodowska University in Lublin, Poland
Josef Dvorak, University of West Bohemia, Czech Republic
Andrey Baybarin, Southwest State University, Russia
Lina Artemenko, National Technical University of Ukraine “Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute”, Ukraine
Anna Lemańska-Majdzik, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Lorena Batagan, Bucharest University of Economics, Romania
Chiraz El Hog, Sousse University, Tunisia
Adam Sulich, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Olga Loyko, Tomsk Polytechnic University, Russia
Diana Fayvishenko, Kyiv National University of Trade and Economics, Ukraine
Ekhlaque Ahmed, Institute of Business Management, Pakistan
Jumadil Saputra, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia
Aurelia Ioana Chereji, University of Oradea, Romania
Katarzyna Grzesik, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Vladimirs Šatrevičs, Riga Technical University, Latvia
Valerii Pavliuk, Co-founder of the NGO "Association of Social Innovations and Scientific Communications", Ukraine
Tatiana Arkadyevna Karandaeva, Mari State University, Russia
Maja Pušnik, University of Maribor, Slovenia
Andreyeva Darya Andreyevna, St. Petersburg State University of Economics, Russia
Aurelia Vasilica Balan, University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine in Bucharest, Romania
Mateusz Gontarz, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Noorul Azwin Md Nasir, Uni. Malaysia Kelantan, Malaysia

Irina V. Sharf, National Research Tomsk Polytechnic University, Russia
Mária Farkasné Fekete, Institute of Economics and Methodology, Szent Istvan University, Hungary
Svetlana Kostina, Ural Federal University, Russia
Ebe Igbino, Covenant University, Nigeria
Ojebola Oluwatunmise, Covenant University, Nigeria
Malgorzata Kutera, Jagiellonian University, Poland
Agung Nugroho, Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia
Zygmunt Kruczek, Academy of Physical Education, Faculty of Tourism and Recreation, Krakow, Poland
Tatiana Nicolaevna Larina, Orenburg State Agrarian University, Russia
Anna Shevyakova, PI Academy "Bolashaq", Kazakhstan
Liudmyla Chvertko, Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University, Ukraine
Adam Ryszko, Silesian University of Technology, Poland
Katarzyna Świercz, Military University of Technology in Warsaw, Poland
Anna Kobińska, University of Life Sciences in Lublin, Poland
James Braman, Community College of Baltimore County, USA
Dragan Benazic, Juraj Dobrila University of Pula, Croatia
Sergei Smirnov, St-Petersburg State University, Russia
Zuliani Dalimunthe, Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia
Dorota Domalewska, War Studies University, Poland
Viktorija Špilova, Daugavpils University, Latvia
Arshad Ahmad, King Saud University, KSA
Imen Chaouachi Allani, University of Carthage, Tunisia
Mukhamediyev B.M., Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Kazakhstan
Agnieszka Szczudlińska-Kanoś, Jagiellonian University, Poland
Arkadiusz Piwowar, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Zied Akrou, University of Sfax, Tunisia
Cecilia Cristina Socorro Gonzalez, Universidad del Zulia, Venezuela
Damir Kalpić, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Mirosław Moroz, Wrocław University of Economics, Poland
Katarzyna Łukasik, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Taiye Tairat Borishade, Covenant University, Nigeria
Olena Reshetnyak, Research Centre for Industrial Problems of Development of the National Academy of Sciences, Ukraine
Jana Mitříková, University of Prešov, Slovakia
Dorin Maier, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, Romania
Alexander Obydenov, Financial University, Russia
Jan Strohmandl, Tomas Bata University in Zlín, Czech Republic
Ruslan Bazhenov, Sholom-Alechem Priamursky State University, Russia
Justyna Zygmunt, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Andreea-Florina Fora, University of Oradea, Romania
Amal Trifa, National School of Computer Sciences, Tunisia
Agnieszka Komor, University of Life Sciences in Lublin, Poland
Arkadiusz Kowalski, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Poland
Nasrine Shah Abushakra, Esol Education, UAE
Ilona Bondos, Maria Curie-Skłodowska University, Poland
Anna Wziętek-Staśko, Jagiellonian University in Kraków, Faculty of Management and Social Communication, Poland
Alexandra Baicoianu, Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania
Joanna Antczak, War Studies University, Warsaw, Poland
Larisa Yu. Ovsyanitskaya, International Institute of Design and Service, Russia
Sunita Lylia Hamdan, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Andrzej Skibiński, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Henry C. Nweke-Love, Landmark University, Nigeria
Anna Saniuk, University of Zielona Góra, Poland
Ivana Bilić, University of Split, Faculty of Economics, Business and Tourism, Croatia

Oses Isibor, Lagos City Polytechnic, Ikeja, Nigeria
Konstantin Shvetsov, Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University (SPbPU), Russia
Tamara Selishcheva, Saint Petersburg State University of Economics, Russia
Felipe Machorro Ramos, Universidad de las Américas Puebla, México
Fitra Lestari, UIN Sultan Syarif Kasim, Indonesia
Iwona Pisz, The University of Opole, Opole
Ismi Rajiani, Lambung Mangkurat, Indonesia
Tamara V. Talanova, Chuvash State University, Russia
Ilham El Haraoui, Ibn Tofail University, Morocco
Miłosz Gac, WSB University in Gdańsk, Poland
Teresa Proença, University of Porto, Faculty of Economics, Portugal
Patrycja Kokot-Stępień, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Alexandra Cristina Dinu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Mariam Mateen Khan, Institute of Business Management (IoBM), Pakistan
Elena V. Butsenko, Ural State University of Economics, Russia
Anna Chechel, Donetsk State University of Management, Ukraine
Feyza Ağlargoş, Anadolu University, Turkey
Ireneusz Miciuła, University of Szczecin
Olga Bucovetchi, University Politehnica of Bucharest, Romania
Anna Sylwia Kowalska, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Anna Mayakova, SWSU, Russia
Ataina Hudayati, Universitas Islam Indonesia, Indonesia
Sebastian Saniuk, University of Zielona Góra, Poland
Marek Szajt, Technical University of Częstochowa, Poland
Isaiah O. Olurinola, Covenant University, Nigeria
Christian Enz, University of South Bohemia, Czech Republic
Aida Matri Ben Jemaa, High Institute of Management (Tunis), Tunisia
Dan Dumitriu, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Anna Mempel-Śnieżyk, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Daniela Zirra, Romanian-American University, Romania
Nataliia Orlova, Professional Development Center of Kiev Region, Ukraine
Marta Nowak, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Lucie Severová, Czech University of Agriculture, Czech Republic
Elena Iadrennikova, Ural Federal University named after the first President of Russia B.N. Yeltsin (UrFU), Russia
Maria Plakhotnikova, Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation, Russia
Elena Lysenko, UrFU, Russia
Anetta Barska, University of Zielona Góra, Poland
Ika Permatasari, Universitas Negeri Surabaya, Indonesia
Lukáš Smerek, Matej Bel University in Banská Bystrica, Slovakia
Alicja Sekuła, Gdansk University of Technology, Poland
Magdalena Sobocińska, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Anita Peša, University of Zadar, Croatia
Francisco Andrés García Barrera, Universidad Arturo Prat, Chile
Liudmyla Melnyk, Uman National University of Horticulture, Ukraine
Marcin Lawnik, Silesian University of Technology, Poland
Małgorzata Macuda, Uniwersytet Ekonomiczny w Poznaniu, Poland
Janusz Wielki, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Viktoria Anatolievna Degtereva, Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Monika Hadaś-Dyduch, University of Economy in Katowice, Poland
Intan Salwani Mohamed, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Malaysia
Sandeep Kumar, Tecnia Institute of Advanced Studies, Affiliated to GGSIP University, New Delhi, India
Marta Starostka-Patyk, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Martha Rodríguez-Villalobos, Universidad de Monterrey, México
Cristian Mera Macías, Universidad Laica Eloy Alfaro de Manabí, Ecuador

Klaudia Przybysz, Wrocław University of Economics & Business, Poland
Jarosław Górecki, UTP University of Science and Technology, Poland
Valery Maslennikov, Plekhanov Russian Economic University, Russia
Nibedita Saha, Tomas Bata University in Zlín, University Institute, Czech Republic
Katarína Rentková, Comenius University in Bratislava, Faculty of Management, Slovakia
Mohammad Kamal Kamel Afaneh, Al Imam Mohammad Ibn Saud Islamic University (IMSIU), KSA
Basel M. Al-Eideh, Kuwait University, Kuwait
Blanka Tundys, University of Szczecin, Poland
Daniela Matušiková, University of Prešov in Prešov, Slovakia
Patrick Omoruyi Eke, Lagos State University, Nigeria
Muntazir Haider Ali, Institute of Business Management, Karachi
Magdalena M. Stuss, Jagiellonian University, Poland
Adebanji W. Ayeni, Landmark University, Nigeria
Monika Kozerska, Częstochowa University of Technology, Poland
Ines Ben Messaoud, University of Gabes / University of Sfax, Tunisia
Konstantin B. Kostin, UNECON, Russia
Oscar Odiboh, Covenant University, Nigeria
Sebastian Kot, Częstochowa University of Technology, Poland
Alla Ivashchenko, Kyiv National Economic University named after Vadim Hetman, Ukraine
Ivana Barišić, University of Zagreb, Faculty of Economics and Business, Croatia
Lubov Afanasjeva, Southwest State University, Kursk, Russia
Alexander Grebenkov, Southwest State University, Russia
Anastasiya Kopytova, Tomsk State Pedagogical University, Russia
Ganna Likhonosova, National Aerospace University «Kharkiv Aviation Institute», Ukraine
Małgorzata Pańkowska, University of Economics in Katowice, Poland
Dyah Setyaningrum, Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia
Maja Mihelja Žaja, Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Justyna Dobroszek, University of Łódź, Poland
Besma Hkiri, Jeddah University, KSA
Irina V. Kokushkina, Saint Petersburg State University, Russia
Elena Vasilyeva, Moscow State University of Civil Engineering, Russia
Anastasiya Peshka, Ural State University of Economics, Russia
IseOlorunkanmi OjO Joseph, Landmark University, Nigeria
Mohammed Adnan Moreb, Altinbas University, Turkey
Fred O. Peter, Covenant University, Nigeria
Boris Tušek, University of Zagreb, Faculty of Economics and Business, Croatia
Katarzyna Tworek, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Poland
Ivana Bulog, Faculty of Economics, Business and Tourism, University of Split, Croatia
Nina Golowko, Self-employed Lecturer, Germany
Olga Ivanovna Solodukhina, Southwest State University, Russia
Galina Bannykh, Ural Federal University, Russia
Joanna WYROBEK, Cracow University of Economics, Poland
Agnieszka Małkowska, University of Szczecin, Poland
Ingrid Majerova, Silesian University in Opava, Czech Republic
Andra-Elena Diaconescu, Politehnica University Timisoara, Romania
Lukas Valek, University of Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic
Boris Miethlich, Comenius University in Bratislava, Faculty of Management, Slovakia
Nataša Šarlija, University of Osijek, Croatia
Stéphane Bourliataux-Lajoie, CNAM Paris, France
Yuliya Karpovich, Perm National Research Polytechnic University, Russia
Daria Elżbieta Jaremen, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Sabina Kubiciel-Lodzińska, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Agboola Mayowa Gbenga, Covenant University, Nigeria
Agnieszka Dobrowolska, Institute of Meteorology and Water Management – National Research Institute, Poland

Fjodor Ruzic, Institute for Informatics, Croatia
Victoria Viaznikova, Mari State University, Russia
Mohammad Falahat, UTAR, Malaysia
Radoslav Jankal, University of Zilina, Slovakia
Natalia Vladimirovna Sharapova, Ural State University of Economics, Russia
Gennadiy Sheptalin, South Ural State University, Russia
Valentina Mikhailovna Sharapova, Ural State University of Economics, Russia
Renata Brajer-Marczak, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Anastasia Ilyina, Kyiv National University of Trade and Economics, Ukraine
Tijani Amara, University of Gafsa, Tunisia
Tatyana Golovina, Central Russian Institute of Management, Branch of RANEP, Russia
Olena Berezina, Cherkasy State Technological University, Ukraine
Victoria B. Malitskaya, Plekhanov Russian University of Economics, Russia
Agnieszka Bieńkowska, Wroclaw University of Sciences and Technology, Poland
S. Jumambayev, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Kazakhstan
Jarosław Olejniczak, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business
Djula Borozan, Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek, Faculty of Economics in Osijek, Croatia
Nawaz Mohamudally, University of Technology, Mauritius, Mauritius
Piotr Bolibok, The John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin, Poland
Cătălina Florentina Albu, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Patrycja Zwiech, University of Szczecin, Poland
Monika Sipa, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Elena Nebolsina, MGIMO University, Russia
Dorota Bednarska-Olejniczak, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Jolanta Maj, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Natalya Sopilko, Russian State Social University, Russia
Elena Davydenko, St. Petersburg State University, Russia
Laurentiu Gabriel Talaghir, Dunarea de Jos University of Galati, Romania
Maria Federica Cordova, UNISA, Italy
Souhir Amri Amamou, University of Tunis, Tunisia
Irina N. Rogova, St-Petersburg State University of Economics, Russia
Bodislav Dumitru Alexandru, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Eva W.L. Lim, UCSI University, Malaysia
Anetta Pukas, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Siti Nuryanah, Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia
Vladimir Nosov, K.G. Razumovsky Moscow State University of technologies and management; Academy of the Investigative Committee of the Russian Federation, Russia
Svitlana Naumenkova, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine
Boris Mucha, Comenius University in Bratislava, Faculty of management, Slovakia
Athanasios Podaras, Technical University of Liberec, Czech Republic
Galina Yu. Fedotova, The Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy and Public Administration, Russia
Mikhail Polevshchikov, Mari State, Russia
Mateusz Chłąd, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Anna Dolinskaia, South Ural State University, Russia
Venera Kubatovna Sabirova, Osh State University, Kyrgyzstan
Katarzyna Szymczyk, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Margarita R. Tsubulnikova, Tomsk Polytechnic University, Russia
Suhail Mohammad Ghouse, Dhofar University, Oman
Piotr Uchroński, WSB University, Poland
Elena Rozhdestvenskaia, Tomsk State University, Russia
Gratiela Dana Boca, Technical University of Cluj Napoca, Romania
Iryna Koshkalda, Dokuchayev Kharkiv National Agrarian University, Ukraine
Rozalia Kicsi, "Ștefan cel Mare" University of Suceava, Romania
Maria Ciurea, University of Petrosani, Romania

Irena Figurska, Pomeranian University in Slupsk, Poland
Tatiana Verevka, Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Andrii Galkin, M. Beketov National University of Urban Economy in Kharkiv, Ukraine
Emeka Okereke, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria
Aleksandra Radziszewska, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Jaya Ganesan, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Dominika Jagoda-Sobalak, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Przemysław Niewiadomski, University of Zielona Góra, Faculty of Economics and Management, Poland
Piotr Wittbrodt, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Sergey Erokhin, Russian State Social University, Russia
Aleksandra Sus, Wroclaw University of Business, Poland
Viktoria Anatolievna Degtereva, Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Iuliia Efimova, Financial University under the Government of RF, Russia
Mercy Ejovwokeoghene Isiavwe- Ogbari, Covenant University Ota, Nigeria
Mikhail Rodionov, Penza State University, Russia
Anna Nowak, University of Life Sciences in Lublin, Poland
Chan Shiau Wei, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore
Sanjay Banerji, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham University, India
Natalya Masyuk, Vladivostok State University of Economics and Service, Russia
Maryna Lohvynova, V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, Ukraine
Małgorzata Okręglika, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Elena Mayorova, Plekhanov Russian University of Economics
Ewa Sobolewska-Poniedziałek, University of Zielona Góra, Poland
Anna Tanina, Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University (SPbPU), Russia
Manique Cooray, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Ioana Andreea Bogoslov, Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Romania
Sylvia Pangsy-Kania, University of Gdańsk, Poland
Ebenezer Bowale, Covenant University, Nigeria
Karlis Kreslins, Ventspils University of Applied Sciences, Latvia
Mario A. Bochicchio, University of Salento, Italy
Dessy Isfianadewi, Universitas Islam Indonesia, Indonesia
Natalia Gorodnova, Ural Federal University, Russia
Ayobami Jolaade, Covenant University, Nigeria
Bogdan Ghilic-Micu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Kateryna Tiulkina, Odessa State Academy of Civil Engineering and Architecture, Ukraine
Emi Normalina Omar, Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM), Malaysia
Karolina Drela, University of Szczecin, Poland
Rand H. Al-Dmour, The University of Jordan, Jordan
Valeriy V. Smirnov, Chuvash State University name I.N. Ulyanov, Russia
Jaishree Asarpota, Higher Colleges of Technology, UAE
Gleb Donin, Czech Technical University in Prague, Czech Republic
Latifah Abd Latib, Universiti Selangor, Malaysia
Tan Choo Peng, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Bruno Barbosa Sousa, IPCA, Portugal
Mikulka Zdeněk, University of Defence, Czech Republic
Johnson Ifeanyi Okoh, National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria
Dike Ike, Ryerson University, Canada
Anna Olszańska, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Jolana Fedorková, University of Defence, Czech Republic
Olawole Olanre Fawehinmi, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia
Olga V. Zaborovskaya, State Institute of Economics, Finance, Law and Technology St Peterburg, Russia
Anna Witek-Crabb, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Agnieszka Wiśniewska, University of Warsaw, Poland
Alexey Bataev, Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Tatjana Vasiljeva, RISEBA University of Applied Sciences, Latvia

Mariya Podshivalova, South Ural State University (SUSU), Russia
Agnieszka Izabela Baruk, Lodz University of Technology, Poland
Natalya V. Alesina, Sevastopol State University, Russia
Julian Jakubowski, Uniwersity of Zielona Góra, Poland
Khaled Mili, King Faissal University, KSA
Afroze Nazneen, University of Jeddah, KSA
Maslin Masrom, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Malaysia
Katarina Tomičić-Pupek, University of Zagreb, Faculty of Organization and Informatics, Croatia
Chijioke Esogwa Nwachukwu, Horizons University Paris, France
Michał Dziadkiewicz, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Sonia Aroussi, Tunis Elmanar University, Tunisia
Sorina-Geanina Stanescu, Valahia University of Targoviste, Romania
Hamed Taherdoost, Hamta Academy & Research Club | Hamta Group, Canada
Lidija Dedi, University of Zagreb, Faculty of Economics & Business, Croatia
Ganama Moustapha Gueme, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Malaysia
Niki Derlukiewicz, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Anna Zabłocka-Kluczka, Wroclaw University of Science and Technology, Poland
Danuta Strahl, Akademia WSB, Polska
Dorota Jelonek, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Marcin Hernes, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Victor S. Voronov, St. Petersburg State University of Economics, Russia
Bidyut Hazarika, Western Michigan University, USA
Rim K. Nurmukhametov, Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federatio, Russia
Larisa Mihoreanu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Georgiy Greyz, South Urals State University, Russia
Milena Ilić, Business Academy in Novi Sad, Faculty of Contemporary Arts Belgrade, Serbia
Abdoulrahman Aljounaidi, Al-Madinah International University Malaysia, Malaysia
Olivia Fachrunnisa, UNISSULA, Indonesia
Aleksandra Zygmunt, Opole University of Technology, Poland
José Alberto Lencastre, University of Minho, Portugal
Fanny Martdianty, Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia
João Paulo Teixeira, Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Portugal
Adebanjo Joseph Falaye, Landmark University, Omu-Aran, Nigeria
Idil Rakhmat Susanto, Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, Indonesia
Teuku Aulia Geumpana, University of Newcastle, Australia
Ionut Laurentiu Petre, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Kamilah Ahmad, UTHM, Malaysia
Georgeta Soava, University of Craiova, Romania
Alaa Salam Jameel, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Malaysia
Ewa Mazur-Wierzbicka, University: of Szczecin, Poland
Yulia A. Dubolazova, Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University (SPbPU), Russia
Rafał Michalski, Wroclaw University of Science and Technology, Poland
Yvonne Lean-Ee Lee, Multimedia University (MMU), Malaysia
Agnieszka Tłuczak, University of Opole, Poland
Ioana Ceaușu, EA – The Entrepreneurship Academy / Humboldt University Berlin / The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Camelia-Daniela Hategan, West University of Timisoara, Romania
Adrian Turek Rahoveanu, UASVM Bucharest, Romania
Martina Blašková, Police Academy of Czech Republic, Czech Republic
Olga Viktorovna Litvinova, Chuvash State Agricultural Academy, Russia
Irina-Adriana Chiurciu, USAMV Bucharest, FMDR, Romania
Aneta Sokół, University of Szczecin, Poland
Alawiya Allui, Prince Sultan University, KSA
Elena Mudrova, Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Sandra Grabowska, Silesian University of Technology, Poland

Ana Elena Maioru, National School of Political and Administrative Studies SNSPA, Romania
Daniela Cristina Momete, University Politehnica of Bucharest, Romania
Afshan Rauf, University of Wollongong, Australia
Marta Kadłubek, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Marius Daraban, Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Romania
Leonilde Reis, Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal, Portugal
Bogdan Florin Filip, "Al.I.Cuza" University of Iași, Romania
Zainab Amin ALSulami, University of Basrah, Iraq
Iustin Ivlev, The Academy of Economic Studies, Romania
Rubina Masum, IQRA University, Pakistan

Disclaimer: The abstracts and papers included in these Conference Proceedings remain the work of the authors and represent their own research / opinion. IBIMA staff have had only non-editorial intervention.

It is IBIMA policy to make reasonable effort to send complete papers to two members of the program committee for full blind peer review and to send a summary of review back to the author(s)

Table of Content

Analysis of The Municipal-Private Partnership Model as a Growth Driver for Single-Industry Towns (Monotowns).....	1
<i>Natalia V. GORODNOVA, Elena G. SHABLOVA, Dmitry L. SKIPIN, Anastasiya A. PESHKOVA and Ivan S. ROZHENTSOV</i>	
Aspects of Corporate Social Responsibility Included in The Integrated Reports: OMV Petrom Case Study...	19
<i>Carmen Florentina PĂUNESCU (PETRE) and Mariana MAN</i>	
Vigor at Work, How Employees’ Perception of Working Time Influence Their Work Satisfaction.....	32
<i>Umar BAIHAQKI, Meila Riskia FITRI and Wulan A. KHAIRUNISA</i>	
Trends of Fast Food among University Students.....	44
<i>Khairunesa ISA and Asliaty ATIM</i>	
Youth’ Willingness and Challenges in Volunteerism : Student Perspective.....	49
<i>Khairunesa ISA, Asliaty ATIM, Fadzlunesa ISA and Johanisma JAMIN</i>	
Transparency in Banking Financial Reporting Evaluation System.....	59
<i>Liviu-Adrian STOICA</i>	
Analysis of Hotspots and Trends of Life Insurance in China.....	67
<i>Fangxiang CHENG and Xindi WANG</i>	
Analysis of The Influence of Process Performance on Organizational Performance: Evidence from Romania.....	77
<i>Andreea BARBU, Gheorghe MILITARU, Valentin-Andrei MĂNESCU, Ramona Alexandra NEGHINĂ and Mihaela-Rodica GANCIU</i>	
Measuring the Value of Creativity in Strategies Formulated by Startups.....	85
<i>Aldona Malgorzata DEREN and Jan SKONIECZNY</i>	
Financial Sustainability of Educational Institutions in Nigeria: Balanced Scorecard Approach and Implications for Policy Designs.....	94
<i>Philip Olawale Odewole, Mary Kehinde Salawu and Rafiu Oyesola Salawu</i>	
Scrum Solo: Application in Projects with a Strong Integration Component.....	109
<i>Joao N. BRITO, Carlos REBELO and Miguel A. BRITO</i>	
Customer Service in Logistics - A Theoretical Framework.....	118
<i>Iwona WASIELEWSKA-MARSZAŁKOWSKA and Katarzyna SAMEK</i>	
Evolution and Modern Solutions in Managing Sales Competitiveness Based on Trade Calculation.....	128
<i>Vladimir A. CHERNOV</i>	
Cloud Project Management.....	138
<i>Bhushan OZA and Peter BUSCH</i>	
Reducing Exchange Rate Risk on The Example of ERP Software.....	153
<i>Marek GAŁĄZKA</i>	
Quality Cost Calculation as Data Source for Kaizen Costing System.....	164
<i>Jozef GRUSZKA and Beata MRUGALSKA</i>	

Basic Principles and The Scorecard of Economic Evaluation of Building Information Modelling Introduction in The Activities of Construction Organizations.....	7138
<i>Sergey BORODIN, Evgeniya MATVIISHINA, Kirill KARDAPOLTSEV, Evgeniy GUSEV and Evgeniia NOVOKRESHCHENOVA</i>	
The Industrial Ecosystem Risks in The Face of Technological Challenges.....	7146
<i>Andrey BYSTROV, Tatyana TOLSTYKH, Nadezhda SHMELEVA and Ayya AGAYEVA</i>	
Russian Accounting in the 17th Century: Details on the Production and Sales of Alcoholic Beverages.....	7157
<i>Svetlana N. KARELSKAIA and Ekaterina I. ZUGA</i>	
Being A Witness or A Victim of Unethical Behaviour Diminishes Employee's Trust in Organisations.....	7166
<i>Remigiusz SZCZEPANOWSKI, Tomasz ZARĘBSKI, Ewelina CICHON and Daria KŁOPOCKA</i>	
COVID-19, Oil Prices and the US Policy Uncertainty.....	7177
<i>Claudiu Tiberiu ALBULESCU</i>	
Technical Modernization of Weapon Systems.....	7182
<i>Kazimierz KOWALSKI</i>	
Principles of Enterprise Potential Management in The Coordinates System of Organizational Development.	7192
<i>KNIAZ SVIATOSLAV, SOPILNYK LYUBOMYR, SHCHEBEL ANDRII, MOROZ SVITLANA, KALASHNYK OLENA, SKRYNKOVSKYY RUSLAN, KRAMAR MARIAN, SPITSYNA ANHELINA, GNYLIANSKA LESIA and LAKIZA VIKTORIIA</i>	
Potential Management of The Enterprise from The Position of Functional Approach.....	7202
<i>KNIAZ SVIATOSLAV, HEORHIADI NELLI, SAI LESIA, SHCHEBEL ANDRII, MOROZ SVITLANA, KALASHNYK OLENA, SPITSYNA ANHELINA, KYRYCHENKO OLENA, VILHUTSKA ROKSOLANA, PEREDALO KHRYSTYNA, MYSKIV IRYNA and SHAYNER HANNA</i>	
The Current Status of Social Entrepreneurship Activity Among Public University Students in Malaysia: Empirical Study.....	7212
<i>Nor Suhaida Bt AWANG, Wan Fauziah Bt WAN YUSOFF and Raudah Bt MOHD ADNAN</i>	
Complex Mechanism of Interaction in the «School-University» System: Approaches to Performance Assessment.....	7220
<i>Nadezhda V. KAPUSTINA, Evgeniya K. KARPUNINA, Navai N. RUSTAMOV, Anastasia A. YUSSUF and Irada T. RUSTAMOVA</i>	
Assessment of The Similarities of Selected European Countries in Terms of Socio-Economic Diversity.....	7228
<i>Małgorzata GRZYWIŃSKA-RĄPCA</i>	
Financial Self-Exclusion: Why Do Households Give Up Activity on the Market of Financial Services and Products?.....	7240
<i>Agnieszka STRZELECKA</i>	
Consumer Purchasing Behaviour and Neuromarketing in the Context of Gender Differences.....	7250
<i>Robert STEFKO, Anna TOMKOVA, Jana KOVALOVA and Ivana ONDRIJOVA</i>	
Historical and Economic Analysis of Scientific Views on The Development of The Agri-Food Market in The Post-Soviet Economic Region.....	7259
<i>Kuraev Aleksey Nikolayevich, Zhakhov Nikolay Vladimirovich, Krivoslykov Vladimir Sergeevich, Melnikova Elena Nikolaevna and Belostotskiy Alexey Alexandrovith</i>	

Principles of Enterprise Potential Management in The Coordinates System of Organizational Development

KNIAZ SVIATOSLAV

Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine, 79013 E-mail: svkniaz@ukr.net

SOPILNYK LYUBOMYR

Lviv University of Business and Law, Lviv, Ukraine, 79021 E-mail: sopilnyk01@gmail.com

SHCHEBEL ANDRII

Lviv University of Business and Law, Lviv, Ukraine, 79021 E-mail: peet_@ukr.net

MOROZ SVITLANA

Poltava State Agrarian Academy, Poltava, Ukraine, 36003 E-mail: smor@meta.ua

KALASHNYK OLENA

Poltava State Agrarian Academy, Poltava, Ukraine, 36003 E-mail: kalashnik1968@meta.ua

SKRYNKOVSKYY RUSLAN

Lviv University of Business and Law, Lviv, Ukraine, 79021 E-mail: uan_lviv@ukr.net

KRAMAR MARIAN

Lviv University of Business and Law, Lviv, Ukraine, 79021 E-mail: kramar.m.o@gmail.com

SPITSYNA ANHELINA

National Transport University, Kyiv, Ukraine, 02000 E-mail: angel7a@ukr.net

KYRYCHENKO OLENA

Higher Educational Establishment of Ukoopspilka "Poltava University of Economics and Trade", Poltava, Ukraine, 36000 E-mail: olena.kyrychenko2010@gmail.com

GNYLIANSKA LESIA

Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine, 79013 E-mail: Lgnylianska@gmail.com

LAKIZA VIKTORIIA

Lviv Polytechnic National University E-mail: viktoriiia.v.lakiza@lpnu.ua

Annotation

Enterprise potential management, as a specific function of management, is implemented by planning the development of enterprise potential, organizing the process of its formation and use, motivating management to rational use of enterprise potential, as well as controlling and regulating the formation and use of capacity. It should be recognized that despite the high level of formalization of the process-functional approach to managing the potential of the enterprise today the object of management is rather poorly formalized, namely - the potential of the enterprise. Due to the diversity of potentials there is a large number of types of their development. The article proposes a system of principles of capacity management in the coordinate system of organizational development. The list of principles is formed so as to level the diversity of potentials of the enterprise, and the coordinate system of organizational development is considered as one that integrates different types of development into one whole.

Keywords: Potential, Management, Organizational Development, Organizational Change, Enterprise.

Cite this Article as: KNIAZ SVIATOSLAV, SOPILNYK LYUBOMYR, SHCHEBEL ANDRII, MOROZ SVITLANA, KALASHNYK OLENA, SKRYNKOVSKYY RUSLAN, KRAMAR MARIAN, SPITSYNA ANHELINA, KYRYCHENKO OLENA, GNYLIANSKA LESIA And LAKIZA VIKTORIIA "Principles of Enterprise Potential Management in The Coordinates System of Organizational Development" Proceedings of the 36th International Business Information Management Association (IBIMA), ISBN: 978-0-9998551-5-7, 4-5 November 2020, Granada, Spain.

Introduction

The development of any business depends on its potential. It should be recognized that, regardless of the type of activity of enterprises, their form of ownership, as well as size, there are certain components of the potential of enterprises that are common to all entities, as well as those that are unique to specific enterprises. This indicates that the potential of the enterprise is a rather complex object of management, which requires technical and technological, information and communication, intellectual and organizational development. The coordinate system of organizational development has an integrative character. It determines the rationality of the formation and use of the enterprise potential. Given this, the urgent task for business leaders is to identify the principles of managing the potential of the enterprise in the coordinate system of organizational development. Unfortunately, nowadays, these principles have been studied in a rather fragmented manner, which indicates the incompleteness of the theory of enterprise capacity management.

Literature Review

The concept of "organizational development" is quite diverse. It is considered as organizational change, as a system of scientific and methodological justification for the preparation and implementation of organizational change, as a set of processes that accompany organizational change, as well as a strategy of enterprise behaviour in the market. Thus, Shcherbyna V. and Popova E. studying organizational development, come to the conclusion that "a stable core of organizational development is the quality of changes that occur, which is determined by the socio-cultural specifics of the organization" (Shcherbyna V., Popova E., 1996). Melnyk S. understands organizational development as "an organized process that disrupts the dynamic development of the organization's structure and directions for achieving a new state of dynamic equilibrium, which will be maintained relatively stably in the renewed structure" (Melnyk S., 2009).

Totsky V. and Lavrenenko V. define organizational development as "a long-term, thorough, comprehensive process of change and development of the organization (enterprise) and the people working in it ...", and also allocate structural (creation of favourable framework conditions for achieving the goals of organizational development through changes in regulation) and personnel (measures for staff development and their incentives for change) aspects (Totsky V., Lavrenenko V., 2005). Gerasymchuk V. considers organizational development as "a large-scale, planned systematized process in the enterprise, which responds to changes in the environment - internal and external" (Gerasymchuk V., 1995).

Novak V. and Rodchenko V. define organizational development as "a process of comprehensive organizational improvement of the system, the purpose of which is to streamline the components of economic activity and transform various parts of the system to maintain long-term life and adapt to changes in the environment" (Novak V., Rodchenko V., 2009). Kolesnikov G. considers organizational development as a process of improving "formal and informal aspects of organizational activities", highlighting among the formal: organizational management structure, management processes, distribution and coordination of rights, duties, responsibilities, organization of work of managers and others. The informal side of organizational activities includes the improvement of knowledge, skills and experience, i.e. training, career growth using effective methods of motivation and formation of corporate culture (Kolesnikov G., 2007). At the same time, Shvindina G. argues that organizational development is a part of the overall strategy of the organization, and the very strategy of organizational development means a system of "direct actions and long-term programmes to initiate and implement constructive changes in organizational architecture for the success of the organization and its members" (Shvindina G., 2016).

The team of authors believes that from the standpoint of a structural approach, organizational development can be presented in such a sequence as: "values, organizational culture, culture of organization, organizational climate, organizational behaviour, organizational interaction" (Gudzynsky, O., Sudomyr, S., Gudzynska, Yu 2012).

Gorbatovska N. considering the theoretical foundations of organizational development of the enterprise in modern conditions of variable environment, defines it as "an organized process that disrupts the dynamic development of the organization and aimed at achieving a new state of dynamic equilibrium, which in the updated structure will be relatively stable" (Gorbatovska N., 2012).

Amelina I. considering the theoretical foundations of organizational development of the enterprise in modern conditions of variable environment, defines it as "an organized process that disrupts the dynamic development of the organization and aimed at achieving a new state of dynamic equilibrium, which in the updated structure will remain relatively stable" ., 2008).

Ladonko L. and Tikhun I. examining existing approaches to defining the essence and goals of the process of organizational development, identified the place and role of strategic organizational changes in innovative development of the enterprise, and reflected the relationship and differences between organizational change and organizational development for a number of factors: level of managerial decision-making, duration of influence, scale of actions, social orientation of the process (Ladonko L., Tikhun I., 2014).

It should be noted that despite the existence of the relationship and interdependence between organizational development and organizational change, but not all organizational change characterizes development, but organizational development is always a change, i.e. the very concept of development involves the implementation of organizational changes that ensure development enterprises.

Thus, organizational development is considered as: a set of concepts and models (theoretical basis) of organizational development; the process of qualitative and structural changes in the organization; practical activities to improve the organization; development strategy.

Thus, organizational development is characterized by the following properties: focus on the medium and long term, focus on the process of change (development), the introduction of change methodology, staff involvement in the process, the use of various methods to achieve goals.

Studies that cover the problems of organizational development have a fairly wide range of subjects that they cover. Nevertheless, they can be divided into those that relate exclusively to theoretical aspects of organizational development (Legeza N., 2019) and those that have a deeply applied focus. Today, most studies belong to the second group. Thus, the authors who study organizational development consider it in the system of assessing the creditworthiness of enterprises, as a stage of technology of financial and analytical management, a component of legitimizing the use of unmanned aerial vehicles, tools for innovation management, a tool for overcoming destructive phenomena in personnel management. empirical and expert evaluation and data analysis.

Zabrodska G.I. and Zabrodska L.D. combining different visions of the essence of this concept rightly note that, "organizational development is a scientific and methodological support for the implementation of long-term programmes of qualitative organizational change, using a systematic set of business processes that adapt to external conditions and internal integration and ensure growth efficiency of functioning and achievement of the purposes of the organization, by perfection of processes of the decision of problems and updating therefore increase of potential of the enterprise is provided..." (Zabrodska G., Zabrodska L., 2017). Agreeing in general with the above interpretation, we note that organizational change is largely beyond the strategic development of the enterprise, and is often implemented at the tactical and operational levels. In addition, it should be noted that organizational change cannot be limited to scientific and methodological support for their implementation.

Organizational decisions should be considered through the prism of the theory and practice of management decisions, as organizational decisions are their subspecies. The scientific literature traditionally distinguishes the stages of technology for making management decisions, namely (Kniaz S., Kulyk Y., Zinkevych D., 2009): formation (identification of the problem situation, analysis of factors that caused the problem situation, consideration of alternative solutions to the identified problems), selection (selection of criteria or criteria by which to choose the best solution from a number of alternatives, analysis of existing alternatives based on the selected criterion (criteria)), approval (documentation of the chosen solution and bringing it to the performers) and implementation (creation of conditions to implement the decision, control and regulate the process of execution of the decision) decision. These stages are also characteristic of organizational decisions. In view of this, organizational changes are a consequence of scientific and methodological support not only for the implementation but also for the formation, selection and adoption of organizational decisions (Kniaz S. et al., 2019).

Purpose of Research

The purpose of the article is to identify and reveal the economic and managerial essence of the principles of enterprise potential management in the coordinate system of organizational development. To achieve this goal, you must perform the following tasks:

- specify the place of the potential of the enterprise in the coordinate system of organizational development;
- identify the starting points of capacity management and establish relationships between them.

Results of the research. As a result of review and analysis of scientific literature there is a reason to say that in the management system of enterprise potential organizational development is a consequence of organizational decisions that can be implemented in three vectors, namely: the vector of organizational structure of enterprise capacity management, the vector of distribution of functions and powers subjects of the management system for managing the potential of the enterprise, as well as the vector of formation and implementation of rules and procedures in the management system of the enterprise relating to the management of the potential of the enterprise. Fig. 1. shows the place of the potential of the enterprise in the coordinate system of organizational development. During the implementation of organizational decisions, the subjects of enterprise management receive information about changes in the characteristics of the object of organizational development, as well as management information from the external environment. On the basis of this information, corrective decisions can be made, often of a tactical and operational nature.

Managing the potential of the enterprise in the coordinate system of organizational development requires the adherence of management to a number of principles. Under the principles of enterprise potential management, we understand the rules, regulations, basic starting points that underlie the process of enterprise potential management and in accordance with which the company will develop. Examining the literature on this issue (Tkachenko S., 2014) found a fairly common approach to the classification of principles into two groups: 1 group - basic (general, general scientific) principles that must be followed at all levels of government; Group 2 – specific ones, which reflect the peculiarities of the functioning of the object of management.

Fig. 1: The place of the potential of the enterprise in the coordinate system of organizational development
 Note: The dotted line shows the feedback from the object to the subjects of management, as well as the receipt of information from the environment to the subjects of management.

Thus, Tkachenko S., studying the processes of functioning of the elements of the subsystem of analytical information processing of functionally developed control systems, identifies a group of basic (system approach, new tasks, unification of design solutions, continuous development, minimization of input and output information, combination of functional and programme-target approach) and specific principles that are formed based on management tasks (Tkachenko S., 2014). However, the application of this approach to the division of principles in relation to the management of the potential of the enterprise into groups is considered inefficient and impractical. Krush P. and Boyko T. describing the components of the management system of production potential of the enterprise, among the principles on which the management system is based are such as, "systemic, reasonable, comprehensive, adaptive, purposeful, dynamic, optimal, predictable, flexible" (Krush P., Boyko T., 2015).

Lyzunova O. and Sirenko Yu. Studying the potential management of a metallurgical enterprise, the basic principles of production potential management include "optimality, objectivity, flexibility, complexity, realism, efficiency, adaptability, organizational innovation" (Lyzunova O., Sirenko Yu. , 2017).

Zakharenko M. among the basic principles of planning the potential of the enterprise refers to the coherence of strategic and current plans; social orientation of the plan; ranking of planning objects according to their importance; adequacy of planned indicators; consistency of the plan with the parameters of the external environment of the components of production potential; variability of the plan, its balance, validity, flexibility (Zakharenko M., 2018).

The author's vision of the classification of the principles of enterprise potential management is shown in Fig. 2, which is necessary to ensure the rationality of the approved organizational decisions.

Fig. 2: Principles of enterprise potential management:

The principle of economic efficiency and safety is also closely related to the principle of applying a scientific approach to managing the potential of the enterprise. In the scientific literature there are author's positions, which argue the feasibility of using an intuitive approach when making decisions of economic nature. The most famous in this direction is J. Soros (J. Soros, 1999), who on the example of the analysis of financial markets and his own

experience made a very successful attempt to put forward a theory of market reflectivity and explain that investors in organized currency and stock markets, decision to buy or the sale of assets is guided by intuition rather than common sense, which is based on deep economic analysis. Admittedly, we can partially agree with this author's theory. Nevertheless, this theory, firstly, applies exclusively to financial markets, and secondly, it reflects only part of reality. There are a number of researchers who use technical analysis of the dynamics of indicators that characterize financial markets and their arguments for decision-making by investors are much more convincing than those of Soros J. For example, Mandelbrot B., studying economics, found that price fluctuations can follow from a latent mathematical order that is not described by standard curves. This assumption was analyzed and proved on the basis of the fractal geometry developed by him. Later, fractal geometry formed the basis of technical analysis of financial markets (Mandelbrot B., Hudson R., 2006), (Williams B, 2000), (Schwager J., 2001). Malishenko K.A. rightly notes that "... fractal market analysis" is a new direction of market forecasting, which is based on the most advanced, of the currently existing, mathematical model. Unlike classical technical analysis, fractal analysis is a scientifically sound method of predicting the price..."(Malyschenko K., 2014).

Based on the above, we note that the application of a scientific approach to managing the potential of the enterprise allows on a systematic basis to analyze objectively the causal links between factors that link in one logical series the reason for the need to form the potential of the enterprise, its state, level of potential consistency of the available potential with the purposes of its formation. There is a reason to believe that the scientific approach is aimed at overcoming subjectivism in decision-making. This task is usually based on a combination of alternative methods of analysis, which allows you to verify the accuracy of the results of the analysis of factors and indicators, as well as through the application of the practice of collegial management decisions.

In the management of enterprise potential, the principle of economic efficiency and safety is basic and it is, to a large extent, related to all other principles. In this case, the essence of this principle should be understood as a bivector criterion, which, on the one hand, has a target - economic benefits from the formation and realization of enterprise potential, and, on the other hand, economic security of the enterprise. For businesses, economic benefits can usually take the form of making a profit, achieving an increase in the market value of equity or assets, acquiring ownership of certain property, including intellectual property rights, and gaining control over other businesses. In turn, economic security, as noted by Sosnovska I.M. "...is a level of protection of all types of enterprise potential from internal and external threats, which ensures stable operation and effective development and requires management by the company's management. The content of this concept includes a system of tools that ensure the competitiveness and economic stability of the enterprise, as well as contribute to improving the welfare of employees..."(Sosnovska I., 2015).

As rightly noted by Georgiadi N.G. "... Economic security reflects the actual and potential level of protection of confidential management information from disclosure, leakage and unauthorized access. The implementation of the principle of economic security in the management of the potential of the enterprise is largely influenced by factors such as financial and technological capabilities of the enterprise; its size and location; nomenclature of products; internal document management system; content, volume and types of confidential information, the level of information education of employees of the enterprise, etc.... "(Georgiadi N., 2009), (Georgiadi N. and others, 2019). In practice, the principle of economic efficiency and safety is implemented through the introduction of an integrated management system using multi-level, combined means of accumulation, storage, processing and use of management information. The introduction of these systems aims to combine automated algorithms for processing economic information with human capabilities of perception and interpretation of data based on poorly formalized factors of internal and external environments of the enterprise. The implementation of these tasks also involves the identification of possible sources of disclosure, leakage and unauthorized access to management information, as well as the development and implementation of measures to protect management information.

The principle of economic efficiency and safety in essence, to some extent, similar to the principle of rationality in the implementation of organizational changes in the management of enterprise potential. However, the concepts of "economic efficiency" and "rationality" are not identical. What they have in common is only the presence of benefit, expediency in application. However, the rationality of organizational change can be measured not by economic indicators, but only by management. For example, by accelerating the processing of management information, reducing interpersonal tension in the workforce, improving the level of perception of change in the organization, and so on. Achieving these and other management effects may be accompanied by certain costs, which in terms of economic efficiency is impractical, but from a managerial point of view is a necessity.

The principle of economic efficiency and safety is also closely related to the principle of applying a scientific approach to managing the potential of the enterprise. In the scientific literature there are author's positions, which argue the feasibility of using an intuitive approach when making decisions of economic nature. The most famous in this direction is J. Soros (J. Soros, 1999), who on the example of the analysis of financial markets and his own experience made a very successful attempt to put forward a theory of market reflectivity and explain that investors in organized currency and stock markets, deciding to buy or the sale of assets is guided by intuition rather than common sense, which is based on deep economic analysis. Admittedly, we can partially agree with this author's theory. Nevertheless, this theory, firstly, applies exclusively to financial markets, and secondly, it reflects only part of reality. There are a number of researchers who use technical analysis of the dynamics of indicators that characterize financial markets and their arguments for decision-making by investors are much more convincing than those of Soros J. For example, Mandelbrot B., studying economics, found that price fluctuations can follow from a latent mathematical order that is not described by standard curves. This assumption was analyzed and proved on the basis of the fractal geometry developed by him. Later, fractal geometry formed the basis of technical analysis of financial markets (Mandelbrot B., Hudson R., 2006), (Williams B, 2000), (Schwager J., 2001). Malishenko K.A. rightly notes that "... fractal market analysis" is a new direction of market forecasting, which is based on the most advanced, of the currently existing, mathematical model. Unlike classical technical analysis, fractal analysis is a scientifically sound method of predicting the price of... "(Malysenko K., 2014).

Based on the above, we note that the application of a scientific approach to managing the potential of the enterprise allows on a systematic basis to objectively analyze the causal links between factors that link in one logical series the reason for the need to form the potential of the enterprise, its state, level of potential, consistency of the available potential with the purposes of its formation. There is reason to believe that the scientific approach is aimed at overcoming subjectivism in decision-making. This task is usually based on a combination of alternative methods of analysis, which allows you to verify the accuracy of the results of the analysis of factors and indicators, as well as through the application of the practice of collegial management decisions.

The following is the principle of focusing the management of enterprise potential on consumer needs of the market. The essence of this principle is that the primary source for establishing or adjusting the goals of forming and realizing the potential of the enterprise is its external environment, and specifically the target audience, i.e. existing and potential consumers of goods or services. Even Henry Ford, said that the purpose of the company is not to make a profit, but to meet consumer needs. He was convinced that only by meeting the needs of certain social groups it is possible to find their place in the market, by achieving a high level of competitiveness and, consequently, it is possible to make a profit (Ford G., 2017). Consumer needs, and especially their change, are indeed important management information that can be the basis for decisions on the formation of a new component of the company's potential or to adjust existing components of the company's potential. These solutions are usually innovative, as they require the use of new production technologies, innovative materials, development of innovative products, introduction of new vectors of work with the target audience in the market, the introduction of innovations in marketing and advertising strategies to promote new products to consumers. Given this, the principle of focusing the management of enterprise potential on consumer needs of the market is directly related to such principles as the principle of compliance with the created supply of goods under international quality standards, as well as the principle of stimulating creativity in managing enterprise potential. In the context of Ukraine's implementation of the course of European integration, especially in the period since the signing of the economic part of the Association Agreement between Ukraine and the EU, the following of the first of these principles is extremely important. The Association Agreement obliged Ukrainian producers, in particular those who are subjects of foreign economic relations with EU countries, to move to European quality standards. This led to the abolition of the so-called GOSTs in force in Ukraine until recently, which after the collapse of the USSR became interstate standards and led to the process of harmonization of DSTU with EU directives and regulations. For example, in the food market, the EU requirements for Ukraine are reduced to the implementation of the NASSP system (system of risk analysis, hazards and control of critical points). Statistics on the implementation of this system are in fact the answer to the question of Ukraine's compliance with EU directives on food safety and organic food. According to the State Food and Consumer Services, by the end of 2019, more than 200,000 enterprises in Ukraine were to implement NAASP, of which 4,540 enterprises had to be audited by the end of 2019. That is, in general, although with a certain slowdown, the implementation of EU standards in Ukrainian legislation is the same as in the implementation of enterprises. It should also be acknowledged that the fastest transition to EU standards is by exporting companies. As for the principle of stimulating creativity in managing the potential of the enterprise, its

essence is to create a creative environment in the team, which, on the one hand, contributes to the readiness of employees to change, and, on the other hand, is conducive to the promotion and implementation of creative ideas, their transformation into technological and product innovations. Practical adherence to this principle in practice is quite a challenge, as numerous studies indicate that many work teams are opposed to change. For employees of enterprises, changes and innovations are associated with the automation of production, job cuts, replacement of people with robots, and so on. In addition, the creation of an environment for employees to produce innovations requires the construction of a flexible system of personnel management, which would be able to: 1) recognize employees who can think creatively and employees who are valuable in clearly defined tasks, able to work in tightly regulated modes of conditions; 2) create appropriate conditions for productive work of both the first and second groups of employees; 3) identification of critical limits of productivity of employees in each of the groups; 4) organization of optimal forms of work of employees of different groups on the implementation of joint projects. Savitska N.V. examining the problems of formation and development of creative potential of enterprises rightly notes that, "... management of creative activity of the enterprise takes place at the strategic and tactical levels... most authors mistakenly identify creative management strategies with innovative strategies of enterprises new products and technologies, a strategy to expand the range of functionality and other properties of existing products and technologies, as well as a strategy to reduce the cost of existing products and technologies. The first of the strategies can be implemented both before and during the commercialization of innovations. In turn, the other two of the selected strategies can be implemented by enterprises only during the commercialization of innovations, in particular at the stage of improvement and modification of innovative products "(Savitska N., 2012). Thus, following the principle of stimulating creativity in the management of the potential of the enterprise requires the formation of the creative potential of the enterprise, building a strategy and tactics for managing it.

Another important principle of enterprise capacity management is to take into account the provisions of the concept of sustainable development. Enterprises are part of both components of sustainable development - the economy and society. Satisfying the consumer needs of society, companies often harm the environment. This is due to economic selfishness and irresponsibility of entrepreneurs to future generations for the opportunity to enjoy the benefits of nature, which are in today's generations (Kniiaz S., 2016). The essence of this principle is to form and develop the potential of the enterprise so that the implementation of the goals set by the enterprise takes into account the needs of modern society, without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs.

Thus, based on the above, we conclude that the selected principles of enterprise potential management constitute a certain system of management visions (Fig. 3), the following of which will contribute to the rationality of the approved organizational decisions.

Fig. 3: The system of principles of enterprise potential management

Note: the numbering of the principles is the same as in fig. 2

The selected principles allow us to focus on the main areas of enterprise capacity management, which will ensure the rationality of the approved organizational decisions.

Conclusions

It is substantiated that the management of enterprise potential is not spontaneous, it is a purposeful process, to ensure the rationality of which it is necessary to apply a systematic approach, in particular in determining key priorities and making decisions on compliance with these priorities. Studies have shown that the basis of systematic management of enterprise potential is a number of interacting principles, namely: the principle of economic efficiency and safety of enterprise potential management; the principle of application of the scientific approach in management of the enterprise potential; the principle of orientation of management of the enterprise potential on consumer needs of the market; the principle of conformity of the created offer of the goods on the conditions of the international quality standards; the principle of stimulating creativity in managing of the enterprise potential; the principle of rationality in the implementation of organizational changes in the management of enterprise potential; the principle of taking into account the provisions of the concept of sustainable development in the management of enterprise potential.

Literature

- [1] Shcherbina, V.V., Popova, E.P. Modern concepts of structural change in organizations, *Sociological Research*, 1996, № 1, 98-106.
- [2] Melnyk, S.G. Theoretical and methodological aspects of organizational development of domestic enterprises, *Bulletin of Khmelnytsky National University*, 2009, № 6, Vol. 2, 46-51.
- [3] Totsky, V.I., Lavrenko, V.V. Organizational development of the enterprise. Totsky, V.I., Lavrenko, V.V. (ed.), Kyiv, KNEU, 2005.
- [4] Gerasymchuk, V.G. Enterprise development: diagnostics, strategy, efficiency. Gerasymchuk, V.G. (ed.), 1995, Kyiv, Higher School, 266 p.
- [5] Novak, V.O., Rodchenko, V.V. Organizational development of international corporations and criteria for its effectiveness. Removed from http://www.nbu.gov.ua/ejournals/PSPE/2009_4/Rodchenko_409.htm.
- [6] Kolesnikov, G.O. Manager's Dictionary. Kolesnikov, GO (ed.), Kyiv, Professional, 2007.
- [7] Shvindina, G.O. Identification of the essence of organizational development strategy, *Intellect XXI*, 2016, № 6, 153-160.
- [8] Hudzynsky, O.D., Sudomyr, S.M., Grudzynska, Yu. S. Management system of institutional transformation of the economy of Ukraine (theoretical and methodological aspect). Hudzynsky, O.D. (ed.), 2012, Kyiv, Agrar Media Group LLC, 771 p.
- [9] Gorbatovska, N.V. Management of organizational development of industrial enterprises (dis ... Candidate of Economic Sciences) .. Makeyevka Institute of Economics and Humanities, 2012. Makeyevka, Ukraine.
- [10] Amelina, I.V. Conceptual bases of organizational development of enterprises in modern conditions, *Project management and production development*, Coll. Science. Ave., SNU. V.Dalya, 2008, №2 (26), 65-71.
- [11] Ladonko, L.S., Tikhun, I.C. Implementation of strategic changes as a key factor in ensuring the organizational development of the enterprise, *Scientific Bulletin of the Chernihiv State Institute of Economics and Management. Series 1: Economics*, 2014, Issue. 1., 126-135.
- [12] Legeza, N.V. Theoretical aspects of organizational support of enterprise development, *Effective Economics*, 2019, № 1, Removed from URL: <http://www.economy.nayka.com.ua/?op=1&z=6855>
- [13] Zabrodska, G.I., Zabrodska, L.D. Organizational development of the enterprise: the basics of defining, *Young Scientist*, 2017, № 4.4 (4.4), 55-59. Removed from <http://molodyvcheny.in.ua/files/journal/2017/4.4/13.pdf>
- [14] Kniaz, S.V., Kulik, Y.R., Zinkevich, D.K. Creative decisions on choosing priority areas of business systems development, *Bulletin of the National University "Lviv Polytechnic". Series "Management and Entrepreneurship in Ukraine: Stages of Formation and Problems of Development"*, 2009, 40 640, 298 - 304.
- [15] Sviatoslav KNIAZ, Stepan STASISHYN, Markiy-Orest SYZON, Serhiy STASEVYCH, Andriy TEREBUKH, Bohdan PSHYK, Yaryna BOHIV and Oleksiy DRUHOV, "Resistance to Change and Market Challenges in the Corporate Governance System" Proceedings of the 34th International Business Management Association (IBIMA), ISBN: 978-0-9998551-3-3, 13-14 November 2019, Madrid, Spain, p. 6922-6928.
- [16] Tkachenko, S.A. Regarding the implementation of general and specific principles in the functioning of the elements of the subsystem of analytical information processing of functionally developed special purpose management systems of industrial enterprises and production associations, including its functional structure, *Effective Economics*, 2014, 1, Removed from http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/efek_2014_1_47.
- [17] Krush, P.V., Boyko, T.O. Management system of production potential of the enterprise in modern conditions, *Entrepreneurship and innovation*, 2015, Vol. 1, 75-83.

- [18] Lyzunova, O.M., Sirenko, Y.I. Management of the potential of a metallurgical enterprise in the system of ensuring the efficiency of its activities, *Bulletin of the Azov State Technical University. Series: Economic Sciences*, 2017, Issue. 33, 27-34.
- [19] Zakharenko, M.M. Organizational and economic principles of formation of the enterprise potential management system, *Investments: practice and experience*, 2018, № 23, 88- 93. doi: 10.32702 / 2306-6814.2018.23.88
- [20] Sosnovskaya, I.M. The concept and importance of economic security of production and economic activities of enterprises, *Effective Economy*, 2015, № 9 Removed from <http://www.economy.nayka.com.ua/?op=1&z=4303>
- [21] Georgiadi, N.G. Integrated management systems for economic development of machine-building enterprises. Kuzmin, O.E. (ed.), 2009, Lviv, Lviv Polytechnic National University Publishing House, 336 p.
- [22] Georhiadi Nelli, Shayda Oksana, Luchko Halyna, Protsyk Iryna, Bohiv Yaryna, Skoropad Iryna, Yemchenko Iryna, Lakiza Viktoriia and Skrynkovskyy Ruslan, "Static-Dynamic and Qualitative Characteristics of Integrated Management Systems for Machine-Building Business Structures" the 35th International Business Information Management Association (IBIMA), ISBN: 978-0-9998551-4-0, 1-12 April 2020, Seville, Spain, p. 1771-1776.
- [23] Soros, J. *The Crisis of Global Capitalism: An Open Society at Risk*. J. Soros (ed.), Kyiv, Osnovy, 1999.
- [24] Mandelbrot, B., Hudson, R. L. (Mis) Behavior of Markets: A Fractal View of Financial Turbulence. Moscow, Williams, 2006.
- [25] Williams, B. *Trading Chaos. Infrared Analysis*, Moscow, RF, 2000.
- [26] Schwager, J. *Technical Analysis. Full course*. Moscow, Alpina Publisher, 2001.
- [27] Malishenko, K.A. Fractal analysis of the securities market, *Effective Economy*, 2014, № 8. Removed from <http://www.economy.nayka.com.ua/?op=1&z=3231>
- [28] Ford, G. *My life and work*. (. Jaman, W. translated from English). Kyiv, Our format, 2017.
- [29] By the end of 2019, 200,000 food companies should implement the HACCP system. - State Food and Consumer Service. Removed from URL: <https://agropolit.com/news/10116-do-kintsya-2019-roku-200-tisyach-pidpriyemstv-harchovoyi-promislovosti-mayut-vprovaditi-sistemu-nassr---derjprodspojivslujba>
- [30] Creative potential of the enterprise as a factor in the formation of innovative technological processes. Kuzmin, OE (ed.), 2012, Lviv, Lviv Polytechnic National University Publishing House, 464 p.
- [31] Savitska, N.V. Management of creative potential of industrial enterprises (dis ... Candidate of Economic Sciences). Lviv Polytechnic National University, 2012. Lviv, Ukraine.
- [32] Kniaz, S. (2015). Transfer potential for innovative development of industrial and trade organizations. *Actual problems of economics*, № 7 (169),

Publication Certification

December 4th, 2020

RE: Paper Publication at the 36th IBIMA International Conference

This letter is to confirm that your paper entitled "Principles Of Enterprise Potential Management In The Coordinates System Of Organizational Development" authored by KNIAZ SVIATOSLAV, SOPILNYK LYUBOMYR, SHCHEBEL ANDRII, MOROZ SVITLANA, KALASHNYK OLENA, SKRYNKOVSKYY RUSLAN, KRAMAR MARIAN, SPITSYNA ANHELINA, KYRYCHENKO OLENA, GNYLIANSKA LESIA and LAKIZA VIKTORIIA was accepted and published at the 36th IBIMA Conference on 4-5 November 2020 Granada, Spain. Conference proceedings (ISBN: 978-0-9998551-5-7, Published in the USA).

The paper will be sent after official publication along with the whole proceedings for indexing by **Web of Sciences, SCOPUS, Engineering Village, etc.** IBIMA International conferences proceedings are indexed by Thomson Reuters (Web of Sciences) since 2006 and by SCOPUS since 2005.

Sincerely

Khalid S. Soliman

Dr. Khalid S. Soliman
36th IBIMA Conference chair

